
CERAMBYCIDAE (COLEOPTERA) RESULTS OF UKRAINIAN EXPEDITION 2021 TO ALBANIA

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[Lazarev, M. A., Gubin, A. I. & Pak, O. V. 2023. Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) results of Ukrainian expedition 2021 to Albania. Munis Entomology & Zoology, 19 (1): 1-23]

ABSTRACT: Ukrainian biologists arranged a short entomological expedition to Albania in May 2021. Many interesting Cerambycidae species were collected. An annotated list of species is presented below. A new subspecies *Tetrops* (s. str.) *praeustus skrylnyki* ssp. n. is described.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, zoogeography, new subspecies, Albania

A collecting trip to Albania (Map 1) 3-23.5.2021 was arranged by 4 persons: A. Gubin (Donetsk), Yu. Skrylnyk (Kharkiv), O. Pak (Donetsk) & I. Plyushch (Kyiv). All materials were identified by M. Lazarev.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material was collected manually. Specimens used in morphological studies were killed by ethyl acetate. All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1 – 30.5 mm 1:2.8 – 4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20. Photos (1-33) were prepared by Yu.E. Skrylnyk, photos (34-35) were prepared by A.I. Gubin, photos (36-37) were prepared by M.A. Lazarev.

Acronyms of collections:

AG – collection of A. Gubin (Donetsk)

IP – collection of I. Plyushch (Kyiv)

MD – collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow)

ML – collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow)

YuS – collection of Yu. Skrylnyk (Kharkiv)

THE WAY OF THE EXPEDITION

Below the whole way of the expedition is shown day by day.

4.5.2021 (Figs. 1-3) – Durrës County in the north environs of Durrës (41°20'47"N, 19°25'36"E, 78 m – 41°20'44"N, 19°25'17"E, 70 m) – 2 km westwards Shetaj village (41°34'04"N, 19°27'54"E, 37 m) [*Deilus fugax* Olivier,

1790, ?*Morimus asper* (Sulzer, 1776), *Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) aethiops maderi* Breit, 1923 and *Neodorcadion bilineatum* Germar, 1823].

5.5.2021 (Figs. 4-6) – along Adriatic Sea to Vlorë County 5.5-7.5 km south-westwards Vlorë – 4 km southwards Kanine village, Lungar Mts., 645-810 m (40°23'37"N, 19°31'10"E). [*Agapanthia (Epoptes) schurmanni* Sama, 1978 (on *Asphodelina taurica*), *Agapanthia (Epoptes) asphodeli asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804) & *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917].

6.5.2021 (Figs. 7-8) – between the Lungar and Rreza e Kana ridges, descending the serpentine of the Çikës ridge to the coast of the Ionian Sea and went towards the city of Sarande to Vlorë County, 17 km north-north-west Sarande, south environs of Lukove village (39°59'N, 19°54'48"E, 150 m) – Vlorë County, 3,5 km east of Vagalat, (39°45'43"N, 20°09'39"E, 81 m) [*Stenopterus rufus geniculatus* Kraatz, 1863, *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917, *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi cynarae* (Germar, 1817), *Agapanthia* (s. str.) *cardui* (Linnaeus, 1767)].

7.5.2021 (Figs. 9-10) – eastwards to the valley between the Lunxhërisë and Kardhiqit ranges, Gjirokastër County, Gjirokastër district, near Saraqinisht village, Lunxhërisë Mts., 900 m (40°7'3"N, 20°13'38"E). [*Chlorophorus figuratus* (Scopoli, 1763) and *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917].

8.5.2021 (Figs. 11-12) – the valley between the ridges Llofiz and Lunxhërisë. Gjirokastër County, 3-5 km eastwards Labovë e Vogël village, Llofiz Mts., 1250-1289-1300 m (40°11'17"N, 20°11'49"E – 40°11'56"N, 20°10'34"E – 41°11'59"N, 20°10'39"E) – Gjirokastër County, 1,6 km northern Saraqinishtë vill., Lunxhërisë Mts., 916 m (40°7'8.07"N, 20°13'32.78"E) [*Stictoleptura (Maculileptura) pallens* (Brullé, 1832), *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917, *Phytoecia (Helladia) flavescens* (Brullé, 1832) and *Tetrops* (s. str.) *praeustus skrylnyki* ssp. n.].

9.5.2021 (Figs. 13-14) – around the Nemërçkës ridge and through the national park Bredhi i Hotoves to Dangëlli, up to Mount Lipecit in Gjirokastër County, 36 km eastward Gjirokastër, 1,5 km northern Vllaho-Psillotarë village (40°6'7"N, 20°33'22"E, 341 m), then to Korçë County, near Leskovik village (40°9'03"N, 20°36'22"E, 940 m), to Radanj village (40°12'39"N, 20°37'45"E, 1105 m – 40°12'59"N, 20°36'52"E, 1086 m) [*Grammoptera* (s. str.) *ustulata ustulata* (Schaller, 1783), *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917 and *Tetrops* (s. str.) *praeustus skrylnyki* ssp. n.].

10.5.2021 (Figs. 15-17) – Korçë County, 1,5 km north-eastward Bregas, That Mts., 1148 m - 1325 m (40°47'40"N, 20°49'35"E – 40°47'39"N, 20°49'32"E) – 2 km southward Voskopoje, (40°37'N, 20°35'54"E, 1321 m) – 5 km S Voskopoje, 4 km E Gjergjeviçë village (40°35'15"N, 20°36'1"E, 1414). [*Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) aethiops sterbai* Breuning, 1944, *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum bravardi* Pic, 1916 and *Tetrops* (s. str.) *praeustus skrylnyki* ssp. n.].

11.5.2021 (Fig. 18) – Korçë County, Pustec Municipality, 3 km southward Leskë, Prespa National Park, Maja Kulles Mt., 1055 m, (40°45'3"N, 20°53'7"E), to Korçë Municipality, 3 km westward Podgorie village, near Pretusha Reservoir (40°49'21"N, 20°45'48"E, 903 m). [*Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lineatocolle* Kraatz 1873, *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) krueperi* Ganglbauer, 1884, *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum bravardi* Pic, 1916 and *Neodorcadion bilineatum* (Germar, 1823)].

12.5.2021 (Fig. 19) – Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1,2 km eastward Fushë Studë village, Kodrules Mts., 1134 m (41°24'16"N, 20°25'10"E) – Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1,5 km westward Ostren I Madh village, Kodrules Mts., 1148 m (41°25'34"N, 20°26'15"E).

13.5.2021 (Fig. 20) – Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6 km NW Shëngjin, Buna River-Velipoja Protected Landscape (41°50'16"N, 19°31'53"E, 5 m).

14.5.2021 – Durrës County, near Durrës (41°20'41"N, 19°25'39"E, 55 m) [*Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) aethiops maderi* Breit, 1923].

15.5.2021 (Fig. 21) – Vlorë County, 10 km north-northwest Vlorë, 2,5 km northwestwards Zvërnec (40°31'22"N, 19°23'19"E, 1 m).

16.5.2021 (Figs. 22-25) – Vlorë County, 7,5 km southwestwards Vlorë, 5 km southwards Kanine village, Lungar Mts., 810 m, 40°23'37"N, 19°31'10"E) [*Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917].

17.5.2021 (Fig. 26) – Vlorë County, Llogara National Park, Maja e Thanasit Mts., 1037 m (40°11'53"N, 19°35'32"E) – 35 km S Vlorë 4 km NW Dhërmi, Delta e Perroit të Palasës, (40°09'51"N, 19°35'24"E, 9 m) [*Stictoleptura (Maculileptura) pallens* (Brullé, 1832), *Stenurella (Priscostenurella) bifasciata intermedia* Holzschuh, 2006, *Clytus (Clytoides) rhamni rhamni* Germar, 1817, *Callimoxys gracilis* (Brullé, 1832), *Stenopterus rufus geniculatus* Kraatz, 1863, *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917].

18.5.2021 (Fig. 27) – Vlorë County, Delvinë Municipality, 0.7 km NE Lefterhor vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 696 m, (39°59'7"N, 20°05'57"E) – 15 km NNE Saranda, Lefterhor vill. env., Kardhiqit Mts., 830 m, (39°59'36"N, 20°06'10"E) [*Dinoptera collaris* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Alosterna tabacicolor tabacicolor* (DeGeer, 1775), *Stictoleptura (Maculileptura) pallens* (Brullé, 1832), *Grammoptera* (s. str.) *ustulata ustulata* (Schaller, 1783), *Clytus* (s. str.) *arietis arietis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Agapanthia (Epoptes) cynarae cynarae* (Germar, 1817)].

19.5.2021 (Fig. 28) – Gjirokastrë County, 13 km northwestwards Gjirokastrë, Taroninë village environs (40°7'31"N, 20°0'16"E, 528 m) [*Stictoleptura (Maculileptura) pallens* (Brullé, 1832)].

21.5.2021 (Figs. 29-31) – Berat County, Skrapar district, 1 km eastwards Korite village, Maja e Kulmakes Mts., 1206 m (40°33'N, 20°16'36"E) [*Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) aethiops sterbai* Breuning, 1944, *Phytoecia (Opsilia) coerulescens coerulescens* (Scopoli, 1763), *Agapanthia (Smaragdula) violacea* (Fabricius, 1775)].

22.5.2021 (Figs. 32-33) – Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6 km NW Shëngjin, Buna River-Velipoja Protected Landscape (41°50'16"N, 19°31'53"E, 5 m – 41°50'22"N, 19°31'41"E) [*Phytoecia (Opsilia) coerulescens coerulescens* (Scopoli, 1763), *Pilemia (Pseudopilemia) hirsutula hirsutula* (Frölich, 1793)].

List of collected taxa

1. *Dinoptera collaris* (Linnaeus, 1758)
2. *Grammoptera* (s. str.) *ustulata ustulata* (Schaller, 1783)
3. *Alosterna tabacicolor tabacicolor* (DeGeer, 1775)
4. *Stictoleptura (Maculileptura) pallens* (Brullé, 1832)
5. *Stenurella (Priscostenurella) bifasciata intermedia* Holzschuh, 2006
6. *Callimoxys gracilis* (Brullé, 1832)
7. *Deilus fugax* (Olivier, 1790)
8. *Stenopterus rufus geniculatus* Kraatz, 1863

9. *Chlorophorus figuratus* (Scopoli, 1763)
10. *Clytus* (s. str.) *arietis arietis* (Linnaeus, 1758)
11. *Clytus* (*Clytoides*) *rhamni rhamni* Germar, 1817
12. *Morimus asper* (Sulzer, 1776) - the exact subspecies identification can't be based here on a single specimen.
13. *Dorcadion* (*Carinatodorcadion*) *aethiops maderi* Breit, 1923
14. *Dorcadion* (*Carinatodorcadion*) *aethiops sterbai* Breuning, 1944
15. *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917
16. *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *etruscum bravardi* Pic, 1916
17. *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *lineatocolle* Kraatz 1873
18. *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *krueperi* Ganglbauer, 1884
19. *Neodorcadion bilineatum* (Germar, 1823)
20. *Phytoecia* (*Helladia*) *flavescens* (Brullé, 1832)
21. *Phytoecia* (*Opsilia*) *coerulescens coerulescens* (Scopoli, 1763)
22. *Pilemia* (*Pseudopilemia*) *hirsutula hirsutula* (Frölich, 1793)
23. *Agapanthia* (*Epoptes*) *boeberi diversicornis* Pic, 1927
24. *Agapanthia* (*Epoptes*) *asphodeli asphodeli* (Latreille, 1804)
25. *Agapanthia* (*Epoptes*) *schurmanni* Sama, 1979
26. *Agapanthia* (s. str.) *cardui* (Linnaeus, 1767)
27. *Agapanthia* (*Smaragdula*) *violacea* (Fabricius, 1775)
28. *Tetrops* (s. str.) *praeustus skrylnyki* **ssp. n.**

1. *Dinoptera collaris* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Acmaeops collaris, Heyrovský, 1934: 134 – “Logara”; 1967: 574, 585 – Albania; Csiki, 1940: 264 – “Rudnik”.

Dinoptera collaris, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 188 – “Tiranë: Mal. i Dajtit”, “Pogradec: Dardhas-Gurikamjes, 1200/1400m”, “Mahde: Q.e Tërhores, NE Bogë, 1800 m”; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 101 – Albania; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 48 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”, “W Großer Prespa-See, zwischen Goricë e Vogël und Liqenas”; Siering & Shumka, 2015: 461 – Librazhd; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 44 – “Pashtrik”, “Koritnik”, “P. K. Llogara”; Danilevsky, 2020: 164 – Albania.

Material. 1 female, Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Munic., 1,5 km NE Varfaj vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'36.28"N, 20°06'10.24"E, 830 m., 18.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG.

2. *Grammoptera* (s. str.) *ustulata ustulata* (Schaller, 1783)

Grammoptera ustulata, Heyrovský, 1934: 134 – “Logara”; 1967: 575, 585 – Albania; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 46 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 42 – “P.K. Llogara”.

Grammoptera (s. str.) *ustulata*, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 101 – Albania.

Grammoptera (s. str.) *ustulata ustulata*, Danilevsky, 2020: 127 – Albania.

Material. 1 male, 1 female, SE Albania, Korçë County, 1 km E Radanj vill., 40°12'38.79"N, 20°37'44.81"E, 1105 m, 9.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 1 male, Albania, Vlorë county, 15 km NNE Saranda, Lefterohor vill. env., Kardhiqit Mts. 830 m, 39°59'36"N, 20°06'10"E, 18.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML.

3. *Alosterna tabacicolor tabacicolor* (DeGeer, 1775)

Alosterna acaicolor, Muraj, 1960: 138 – “Zall-Dardhë”, misspelling.

Alosterna tabacicolor, Heyrovský, 1967: 575, 586 – Albania; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 195 – “Tiranë: Mal. i Dajtit”.

Alosterna tabacicolor tabacicolor, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 96 – Albania; Siering & Shumka, 2015: 460 – Librazhd; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 42 – “P.K. Llogara”; Danilevsky, 2020: 120 – Albania.

Material. 3 males, S Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Municipality, 0.7 km NE Lefterhor vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'6.73''N, 20°5'57.13''E, 696 m, 18.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 1 male, 1 female, Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Munic., 1,5 km NE Varfaj vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'36.28''N, 20°6'10.24''E, 831 m., 18.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG.

4. *Stictoleptura (Maculileptura) pallens* (Brullé, 1832)

Leptura pallens, Heyrovský, 1967: 575, 587 – Albania, “Borshi südlich Vlora, Mali i Çorajt, 700-1100 m”, “Borshi südlich Vlora, Flußtal des Lumi i Borshit”, “Borshi südlich Vlora, SW-Hang mit *Pistacia lentiscus*, *Phlomis fruticosa*, 200-400 m”, “Poliçan westlich Tomor, 500 m”, “Dajti, Shkall Prisk, 850 m”.

Stictoleptura (s. str.) *pallens*, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 115 – Albania.

Stictoleptura pallens, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 193 – Albania: “Tiranë: Mal. i Dajtit”; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 47 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 43 – “P.K. Butrinti”; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 193 – “Tiranë: Mal. i Dajtit”.

Stictoleptura (Maculileptura) pallens, Danilevsky, 2020: 147 – Albania.

Material. 1 female, Albania, Gjirokastrë county, 13 km NNE Gjirokastrë, Liofiz Mts. Cajup Field, 41°11'59''N, 20°10'39''E, 1300 m, 8.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Albania, 35 km S Vlorë 4 km NW Dhërmi, Delta e Perroit të Palasës, 40°09'51''N, 19°35'24''E, 9 m, 17.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML; 7 males, 2 females, S Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Municipality, 0.7 km NE Lefterhor vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'6.73''N, 20°5'57.13''E, 696 m, 18.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 1 male, Albania, Gjirokastrë County, 13 km NW Gjirokastrë, Taroninë vill. env., 40°7'31.42''N 20°0'15.66''E, 528 m., 19.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS.

5. *Stenurella (Priscostenurella) bifasciata intermedia* Holzschuh, 2006

Strangalia bifasciata, Heyrovský, 1934: 134 – “Maja e Trvol”, “Tomor”, “Devoll-Tal”; 1937: 89 – “Lum i Tiranës”; 1967: 575, 592 – Albania, “Borshi südlich Vlora, Mali i Çorajt, 700-1100 m”, “Borshi südlich Vlora, SW-Hang”, “Poliçan westlich Tomor, Kulturland, 500 m”, “Iba unterhalb Krraba, 400 m”, “Lurja östlich Kurbneshi, Lan Lura”; Csiki, 1940: 266 – “Ipek”, “Djakova”, “Tropoja”, “Kula Ljums”, Stičen (in radices Montibus Djalic Ljums)”, “Radomir”; Schatzmayr, 1943: 132 – “di Lushnja, Terpan e Fushes Dukati”; Muraj, 1960: 139 – “Korab”, “Lurë”, “Radomirë”; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 196 – “Durrës: Bizë”, “Korcë: Rez. i Gjançit (S Korcë) 1000 m”, “Përmet: 12 Km W Përmet, Pocomit”, “Pukë: Lathizë, 1100 m”, “Shkodër: Mali Kolaj”, “Tiranë: Mal. i Dajtit”, “Burrel: Velez”, “Mahde: Q.e Tërhores, NE Bogë”; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 47 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”, “Lebensräume entlang der Verbindungsstraße Eingang zum Nationalpark N Zvezdë bis zur albanisch/mazedonischen Grenze N Goricë e Madhe, auch Uferbereiche des Kleinen Prespa-Sees”.

Stenurella bifasciata bifasciata, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 196 – “Durrës: Bizë”, “Korcë: Rez. i Gjançit (S Korcë) 1000 m”, “Përmet: 12 Km W Përmet, Pocomit”, “Pukë: Lathizë, 1100 m”, “Shkodër: Mali Kolaj”, “Tiranë: Mal. i Dajtit”, “Burrel: Velez”, “Mahde: Q.e Tërhores, NE Bogë”; Siering & Shumka, 2015: 460 – Librazhd, “Dorëz”, “Togëz”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 43 – “Pashtrik”, “SE Butrint bei Mursi”, “P. K. Butrinti; Ksamil”, “Küste; Orikum”, “Koritnik”, “Küste; bei Orikum; Rruga Sazani”, “Küste; E Orikum; Tragjas”, “N Piskupat (L. i Ohrid)”, “6 km SE Librazhd; Shkumbin-Tal”,

“Zentral-Albanien; zwischen Pörrenjas und Qukös”, “P. K. Butrinti; lichte Altbaum-Bestände und Gebüsche”, “SE Butrint; Mursi”, “S Gjirokastör; Bistricö”, “S Gjirokastär; Bergland; Krongj”, “S Gjirokastör; Pass Q. e Muzinös; 536 m ü. NN”.

Stenurella bifasciata intermedia, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 233 – “Albania: Ersekë: 20/30 Km S Ersekë”.

Stenurella (Priscostenurella) bifasciata intermedia, Danilevsky, 2020: 145 – Albania.

Material. 1 male, Albania, 35 km S Vlorë 4 km NW Dhërmi, Delta e Perroit të Palasës, 40°09'51"N, 19°35'24"E, 9 m, 17.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML.

6. *Callimoxys gracilis* (Brullé, 1832)

Callimoxys gracilis, Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 49 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”; Danilevsky, 2020: 285 – Albania.

Material. 1 female, SW Albania, Vlorë County, Liogara National Park, Maja e Thanasit Mts., 40°11'52.72"N, 19°35'32.38"E, 1037 m, 17.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS.

7. *Deilus fugax* (Olivier, 1790)

Deilus fugax, Siering & Beier, 2014: 254 – Albanien; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 45 – “Küste; Orikum; Rruga Sazani”; Danilevsky, 2020: 257 – Albania.

Material. 2 males. 1 female, Albania, Durrës County, N env. of Durrës, 41°20'43.73"N, 19°25'16.70"E, 70 m., 4.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 1 female, Albania, Vlorë County, 10 km NNW Vlorë, 2,5 km NW Zvërnec, 40°31'22.04"N, 19°23'18.88"E, 1 m., seashore, 15.05.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG.

8. *Stenopterus rufus geniculatus* Kraatz, 1863

Stenopterus rufus a. geniculatus, Heyrovský, 1934: 134 – “Tepelene”, “Giovanni di Medua”; Csiki, 1940: 266 – “Rudnik”, “Mons Peklen (1500 m)”.

Stenopterus rufus, Csiki, 1940: 266 – “Mons Peklen (1500 m)”; Schatzmayr, 1943: 132 – “Fushes Dukati”; Heyrovský, 1967: 576, 597 – Albania, “Iba unterhalb Krraba, 400 m”, “Borshi südlich Vlora”, “U ji Ftohte südlich Tepelena, 200 m”, “Polican, westlich Tomor, Kulturland, 500 m”, “Polican westlich Tomor, *Arbutus-Phillyrea-M&ccchie*, 500 m”, “Dajti, Shkall Prisk, 850 m”, “Dajti, Westhang, 1100 m”, “Mali me Grope, Livadhet e Selites, Wiese in 1000-1100 m”, “Bize bei Shengjergji, Wiesen in Rotbuchenzzone, 1400-1500 m”, “Nordalbanische Alpen, Thethi, Shalabach-Tal bei Thethi, 900-1200 m”; Muraj, 1960: 139 – “Korab”, “Lurë”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 46 – “P. K. Butrinti; N Ksamil; Man. i Shöngjerg”, “Küste; Orikum; Rruga Sazani”, “P. K. Llogara”, “Küste; E Orikum”, “P. K. Bredhi i Drenovös”, “Küste; E Orikum; Tragjas”, “6 km SE Librazhd; Shkumbin-Tal”, “S Gjirokastör; Pass Q. e Muzinös; 536 m ü. NN”.

Stenopterus rufus geniculatus, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 205 – Albania; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 206 – “Pukë; Lathizë, 1100 m”, “Peshkopi: Mal. i Arithit”, “Mahde: Q.e Tërhores, NE Bogë”; Plewa & al., 2018: 181 – Albania: “County Korçë: Gozhdarzhde at Gërmenj, 990 m a.s.l.”, “County Gjirokaster: Benjë at Përmet, 280 m a.s.l.”, “County Vlorë: Llogara, Mts Çikës, 1200 m a.s.l.”, “County Vlorë: Akerni at Zvërnec”, “County Shkodër: Qafe Malit at Fushë-Arrëz, 950 m a.s.l.”, “County Shkodër: Bërdicë at Trush, 30 m a.s.l.”, “County Shkodër: Hani i Hotit at Ivanaj, 15 m a.s.l.”; Danilevsky, 2020: 288 – Albania.

Material. 1 male, Albania, Vlorë County, 3,5 km E Vagalat, 39°45'43.02"N, 20°9'39.46"E, 81 m, 6.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 1 male, 1 female, Albania, Vlorë County, 17 km NNW Sarande, S env. of Lukove vill., 39°58'20.50"N 19°54'58.50"E, 32 m., 17.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG.

9. *Chlorophorus figuratus* (Scopoli, 1763)

Chlorophorus figuratus, Heyrovský, 1934: 135 – “Maja e Trvol”, “Bushek”, “Iba Arsen”; 1937: 89 – “Lum i Tiranes”; 1967: 577 – “Borshi südlich Vlora, litorale Terrasse mit Olea und Ficus, 50-150 m”, “Iba unterhalb Krraba, 400 m”, “Nordalbanische Alpen, Thethi, Shalabach-Tal bei Thethi, 900-1200 m”; Csiki, 1940: 267 – “Rudnik”, “Ipek”, “Mons Peklen”, “Stičen”; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 166 – Albania; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 213 – “Okol di Boga”, “Dures: Bizë”, “Shkodër: M. e Ghzoprës (W slopes), 400 m”, “Ersekë: 20/30 Km S Ersekë”, “Pogradec: Dardhas-Gurikamjes, 1200/1400 m”, “Mahde: Q.e Tërhores, NE Bogë”; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 48 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”, “zwischen Goricë e Vogël sowie 3 km S der ersten Abfahrt nach Liqenas”; Siering & Shumka, 2015: 461 – Librazhd, “Dorëz”; Danilevsky, 2020: 228 – Albania; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 45 – “Küste; E Orikum; Umgebung Tragjas”, “Küste; bei Orikum; Rruga Sazani”, “Zentral-Albanien; zwischen Pörrenjas und Qukes; vermülltes Ödland mit vielen Blütenpflanzen; zwischen L. i Shkumbinit und Straße”, “P.K. Butrinti”;

Chlorophorus figuratus, Muraj, 1960: 140 – “Kodrat e Fierit”, misspelling.

Chlorophorus (Humeromaculatus) figuratus, Plewa & al., 2018: 180 – “County Gjirokaster: Benjë at Përmet, 280 m a.s.l.”, “County Fier: Divjaka at Lushnja”, “County Shkodër: Qafe Malit at Fushë-Arrëz, 950 m a.s.l.”, “County Shkodër: Oblikë at Zus”.

Material. 1 female, SW Albania, Gjirokastër County, Gjirokastër distr., Saraqinisht vill., Lunxhërisë Mts., 40°7'2.61''N, 20°13'37.68''E, 900 m, 7.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. – YuS.

10. *Clytus* (s. str.) *arietis arietis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Clytus arietis arietis, Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 49 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”, “Kernzone: Goricë e Vogël und Gollomboç”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 45 – “P.K. Llogara; lockere Altholz-Bestände Kiefer/Tanne”, “P.K. Bredhi i Drenovës”; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 170 – Albania; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 211 – “Albania: Okol di Boga”, “Mahde: Q.e Tërhores, NE Bogë, 1800 m”.

Clytus arietis, Csiki, 1940: 267 – “Mons Peklen”.

Clytus (s. str.) *arietis arietis*, Plewa & al., 2018: 180 – “County Shkodër: Qafe Malit at Fushë-Arrëz, 950 m a.s.l.”; Danilevsky, 2020: 233 – Albania.

Material. 1 female, S Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Municipality, 0.7 km NE Lefterhor vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'6.73''N, 20°5'57.13''E, 696 m, 18.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. – YuS; 1 female, S Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Munic., 1.5 km NE Varfaj vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'36.28''N, 20°06'10.24''E, h-831 m., 18.05.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. – AG.

11. *Clytus* (*Clytoides*) *rhamni rhamni* Germar, 1817

Clytus rhamni, Heyrovský, 1934: 134 – “San G. di Medua”, “Barande”, “Mato Hasanaj”, “Bushek”, “Ljum i Skumbin”; 1937: 89 – “Lum i Tiranes”; 1967: 577, 602 – Albania, “Borshi südlich Vlora”, “Borshi südlich Vlora, Mali i Qorajt, 700-1100 m”, “Borshi südlich Vlora, Flußtal des Lumi i Borshit”, “Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena, 200 m”, “Poliçan westlich Tomor, Kulturland, 500 m”, “Iba unterhalb Krraba, 400 m”, “Dajti, Shkall Prisk, 850 m”; Csiki, 1940: 267 – “Stičen”; Schatzmayr, 1943: 133 – “Fushes Dukati e Terpan”; Muraj, 1960: 140 – “Shkallë-Priskë”; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 211 – “Albania: Okol di Boga”, “Ersekë: 20/30 Km S Ersekë”, “Tiranë: Mal. i Dajtit”, “Pogradec: Dardhas-Gurikamjes, 1200/1400 m”; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 171 – Albania; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 49 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”: “zwischen Goricë e Vogël sowie 3 km S der ersten Abfahrt nach Liqenas”; Siering & Shumka, 2015: 461 – Librazhd, “Togëz”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 45 – “P. K. Butrinti; Ksamil und Umgebung”, “P. K. Butrinti; N Ksamil; Man. i Shöngjerg”, “P. K. Butrinti; Ksamil”, “E

Orikum; Umgebung Tragjas", "6 km SE Librazhd; Shkumbin-Tal", Zentral-Albanien; zwischen Pörrenjäs und Qukös".

Clytus rhamni rhamni, Danilevsky, 2012: 142 – Albania; 2020: 234 – Albania.

Material. 1 male, Albania, 35 km S Vlorë 4 km NW Dhërmi, Delta e Perroit të Palasës, 40°09'51"N, 19°35'24"E, 9 m, 17.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Albania, Vlorë County, 17 km NNW Sarande, S env. of Lukove vill., 39°58'20.50" N 19°54'58.50"E, 32 m., 17.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG.

12. *Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) aethiops maderi* Breit, 1923

Dorcadion maderi Breit, 1923: 147, 148 – "Südalbanien", "Vora, Albanien", "Kruja, Albanien", "Durc", "Elbassan, Albanien"; Heyrovský, 1934: 135 – "Tiranë", "Ljumi Skumbin"; 1967: 580, 610 – Albania, "Mali me Grope, Livadhet e Selites, Wiesen in 1000-1100 m", "Mali me Grope, 1200 m", "Tomor, Kloster Abbäs-Ali, 1800 m"; Schatzmayr, 1943: 133 – "Lushnja".

Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) maderi, Breuning, 1958: 34 – Albania; 1962: 517 – "Albanien: Vora, Kruja, Elbassan; Tirana, Berat"; Danilevsky, 2010a: 242 – Albania; 2020: 339 – Albania; Plewa & al., 2018: 181 – "County Dibrë: Fushë Studë at Steblevë, 1100 m a.s.l."

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) aethiops, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 218 – "Durazzo".

Dorcadion aethiops, Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 47 – "Elbasan; Mali i Shpatit".

Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) aethiops maderi, Danilevsky & Tavakilian, 2022: 141 – "Vora, Kruja, Elbasan".

Material. 3 males, 2 female, Albania, Durrës County, N env. of Durrës, 41°20'43.73"N, 19°25'16.70"E, h-70 m., 4.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 6 males, 2 female, Albania, Durrës County, N env. of Durrës, 41°20'41.42"N, 19°25'39.32"E, 55 m., 14.5.2021, Gubin A.I. leg - AG; 7 females, SW Albania, Durrës County, near Durrës, 41°20'41.42' N, 19°25'39.32' E, 55 m, 14.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS.

13. *Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) aethiops sterbai* Breuning, 1944

Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) sterbai Breuning, 1944: 14 – "Albanie: Moskopolië"; 1958: 34 – Albania; 1962: 519 – "Albanien: Moskopolje", "Kulmak"; Danilevsky, 2010a: 243 – Albania; 2020: 339 – Albania.

Dorcadion sterbai, Heyrovský, 1967: 580, 611 – Albania.

Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) aethiops sterbai, Danilevsky & Tavakilian, 2022: 141 – "Moskopolje = Voskopoje, Kulmak".

Material. 1 male, Albania, Korçë County, Korçë distr., 2 km S Voskopoje, 40°36'59.73"N 20°35'53.84"E, 1321 m, 10.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 1 female, Albania, Berat County, Skrapar distr., 1 km E Korite vill., Maja e Kulmakes Mts., 40°33'0.06"N, 20°16'36.27"E, 1206 m, 21.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS.

14. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917

? *Dorcadion fuscifrons* Chevrolat, 1882: 60 – "Albania".

Dorcadion femoratum v. *valonense* Pic, 1917: 6 – "Albanie occidentale".

Dorcadion valonense Apfelbeck, 1923: 145, 148, 149 – "Valona, Šen Thanas und Pašaliman in Albanien"; Heyrovský, 1967: 579, 609 – Albania, "Dajti, Shkall Prisk, 850 m", "Dajti, Westhang, 1100 m"; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 47 – "Tirane; Mal i Dajt".

Dorcadion apfelbecki Winkler, 1929: 1188 – "Albanien"; Schatzmayr, 1943: 134 – "Lushnja".

Dorcadion apfelbecki a. *jedličkai* Heyrovský, 1937: 89, 91 – "Albanien: Maja e Konigskol, Seraqin".

- Dorcadion etruscum* a. *valonense*, Heyrovský, 1937: 89 – “Kara Ali Bey”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense* m. *grisellum* Breuning, 1946: 115 – “Valonia, Albanie”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense* m. *albosuturale* Breuning, 1946: 115 – “Mal-i-Dhatit, Albanie”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense* m. *femorale* Breuning, 1946, 115 – “Argyrokastron, Albanie”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense* m. *apicesignatum* Breuning, 1946: 115 – “Argyrokastron, Albanie”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) etruscum* m. *fuscifrons*, Breuning, 1962: 347 – Albania: “Albanien” [40°49'N 19°35'E].
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) albosuturale* Breuning, 1962: 351 – Albanien; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 218 – “Ardenica”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense*, Breuning, 1962: 350 – “Südliches Albanien: Valona, Kosuf Planina”; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 217 – “Tirana, c/o Facoltà di Agraria”, “Monte Dajti (Tirana prov.)”.
- Dorcadion albosuturale*, Heyrovský, 1967: 579, 610 – Albania; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 47 – “Erseke; 5 km SW Kolonje”.
- Dorcadion etruscum*, Heyrovský, 1967: 579. – “Albanien”.
- Dorcadion lugubre*, Heyrovský, 1967: 579, 610 – Albania, “Tomor, Kloster Abbas-Ali, 1800 m”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 47 – “Küste; Oriikum”, “Küste; SE Oriikum; Dukat Fshat und Umland”, “P.K. Llogara”.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lugubre*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 249 – Albania.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) albosuturale*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 243 – Albania; 2010b: 233 – Albania; 2020: 340 – Albania.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) valonense*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 254 – Albania; 2020: 359 – Albania.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) etruscum*, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 217 – “Beart, passo circa 22 km sud Beart”.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum*, Plewa & al., 2018: 181 – “County Korçë: Radanj at Gërmenj, 1060 m a.s.l.”, “County Vlorë: Llogara, Mts Çikës, 1200 m a.s.l.”.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense*, Lazarev, 2023b: 441 – Albania: “Valona (now Vlorë)”.

Material. 1 male, Albania, 7 km SE Vlorë, Kanine vill., 700 m, 16.5.2021, O. Pak - MD; 7 female, 3 females, S Albania, Vlorë County, 7,5 km SW Vlorë, 5 km S Kanine vill., Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45''N, 19°31'10.09''E, 810 m, 5.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 19 males, 13 female, Vlorë, 4,5 km S Kaninë, 40°23'57.34''N, 19°31'5.06''E, 757 m, 5.5.2021, A.I. Gubin - AG; 1 male, S Albania, Gjirokastër County, Gjirokastër distr., near Saraqinisht vill., Lunxhërisë Mts., 40°7'2.61''N, 20°13'37.68''E, 900 m, 7.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 7 males, 2 females, Albania, Gjirokastër County, 1,6 km N Saraqinishtë vill., Lunxherise Mts., 40°7'8.07''N, 20°13'32.78''E, 916 m., 7.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 2 males, S Albania, Gjirokastër County, 3 km E Labovë e Vogël vill., Llofiz Mts., 40°11'56.30''N, 20°10'37.65''E, 1289 m, 8.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 3 males, Albania, Gjirokastër county, 13 km NNE Gjirokastër, Liofiz Mts. Cajup Field, 41°11'59''N, 20°10'39''E, 1300 m, 8.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Girokastër, 1.6 km N Sarakinishtë, Lunxhërisë Mts., 40°7'8.07''N, 20°13'33''E, 916 m, 8.5.2021, A.I. Gubin - AG; 3 males, Albania, Korçë County, 1 km NW Radanj vill., 40°12'56.98''N 20°36'30.40''E, 1100 m, 9.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 28 males, 12 females, SW Albania, Vlorë County, 7,5 km SW Vlorë, 5 km S Kanine vill., Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45''N, 19°31'10.09''E, 810 m, 16.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 63 males, 14 females, Albania, Vlorë County, 7 km SW Vlorë, Kanine vill. env. Lungar Mts., 770 m, 16.5.2021, I. Plushch leg. - IP; 4

male, 2 females, Vlorë, 4.5 km S Kaninë, 40°23'57.34''N, 19°31'5.06''E, 757 m, 16.5.2021, A.I. Gubin - AG; 42 males, 12 females, Albania, Vlorë County, 7,5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45''N, 19°31'10.09''E, 810 m., mountain meadows, 16.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 2 males, SW Albania, Vlorë County, Llogara National Park, Maja e Thanasit Mts., 40°11'52.72''N, 19°35'32.38''E, 1037 m, 17.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 1 male, Albania, Vlorë County, Llogara National Park, Maja e Thanasit Mts., 40°11'52.72''N, 19°35'32.38''E, 1037 m., 17.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 1 male, Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Munic., 1,5 km NE Varfaj vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'36.28''N, 20°06'10.24''E, 831 m., 18.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 1 male, Albania, Berat County, Skrapar distr., near Korite vill., Maja e Tomorit Mts., 40°33'00.34''N, 20°16'14.95''E, h-1175 m., 21.5.202, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG.

15. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum bravardi* Pic, 1916

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense m. *albosuturale* Breuning, 1946: 115 – “Mal-i-Dhatit, Albanie” (unavailabl name).

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) albosuturale Breuning, 1962: 351 – “Albanien: Mal-i-that”.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) bravardi, Breuning, 1962: 352 – “Albanien: Mal-i-that”.

Dorcadion bravardi, Heyrovský, 1967: 579, 610 – “Albanien”.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) bravardi, Özdikmen, 2010: 430 – Albania; Danilevsky, 2010a: 244 – Albania.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) etruscum bravardi, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 217 – “Albania: Mal i That”.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum bravard, Lazarev, 2023b: 443 – “South-eastern Albania, Mal-i-That environs, Prespa National Park, penetrates to Greece and North Makedonia”.

Material. 3 males, 2 females, SE Albania, Korçë County, 3 km S Leskë, Prespa National Park, Maja Kules Mts., 40°45'3.38''N, 20°53'7.49''E, 1055 m, 11.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 1 male, Albania, Korçë county, Thate Mts., Bregas vill. env., 40°47'39''N, 20°49'32''E, 1325 m, 10.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML.

16. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lineatocolle* Kraatz 1873

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lineatocolle, Siering, 2014: 76 – “Albanien: Prespa-Nationalpark”; Kovács et al., 2015: – “Albania, Kolonjë district, Grammos Mts, Rehovë, N40°20.111', E20°43.467', 1445 m”, “Librazhd district, Karkavec S 0.5 km, right bank of Lumi i Shkumbinit, roadside ditch, N41.0526°, E20.4837°, 440 m”; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 50 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”, zwischen Kallamas, Goricë e Vogël und Liqenas, auch im Bergland NW Goricë e Vogël ; Plewa & al., 2018: 181 – “County Korçë: Radanj at Gërmenj, 1060 m a.s.l.”; Danilevsky, 2020: 349 – Albania.

Material. 9 males, Albania, Korçë County, Pustec Municipality, 3 km S Leskë, Prespa National Park, Maja Kules Mts., 40°44'38.46''N 20°52'59.31''E, h-1060 m., 11.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG.

17. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) krueperi* Ganglbauer, 1884

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) krueperi, Pic, 1927: 161 – “Albanie: Stavora (env. de Koritza)”; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 215, 216 – Albania: Stavora (env. de Koritza).

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) krueperi, Danilevsky, 2010a: 248 – Albania; 2020: 348 – Albania.

Material. 2 males, SE Albania, Korçë County, Korçë Municipality, 3 km W Podgorie vill., near Pretusha Reservoir, 40°49'21.51''N, 20°45'48.37''E, 903 m, 11.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS.

18. *Neodorcadion bilineatum* (Germar, 1823)

Neodorcadion bilineatum, Heyrovský, 1934: 135 – “Iba Arsen”, “Mali-Dajtit”; 1937: 90 – “Tiranë”; 1967: 578, 608 – Albania, “Iba unterhalb Krraba, 400 m”; Danilevsky, 2010a: 263 – Albania; 2020: 371 – Albania; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 213 – “Durazzo”; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 50 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”, “Kallamas, zwischen Goricë e Vogël und Liqenas, auch im Bergland NW Goricë e Vogël”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 47 – “SE Butrint bei Mursi”; Plewa & al., 2018: 181 – “County Korçë: Radanj at Gërmenj, 1060 m a.s.l.”; Danilevsky, 2023: 316 – Albania.

Material. 1 male, 2 female, Albania, Durrës County, N env. of Durrës, 41°20'43.73''N, 19°25'16.70''E, h-70 m., 4.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 2 males, SE Albania, Korçë County, 3 km Leskë, Prespa National Park, Maja Kulles Mts., 40°45'3.38''N, 20°53'7.49''E, 1055 m, 11.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 2 males, 1 female, Albania, Durrës County, N env. of Durrës, 41°20'41.42''N, 19°25'39.32''E, h-55 m., 14.5.2021, Gubin A.I. leg. - AG.

19. *Phytoecia (Helladia) flavescens* (Brullé, 1832)

Helladia flavescens, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 231 – “Coritza”.

Phytoecia (Helladia) flavescens, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 303 – Albania; Danilevsky, 2020: 435 – Albania.

Material. 1 male, S Albania, Gjirokastër County, 3 km E Labovë e Vogël vill., Llofiz Mts., 40°11'56.30''N, 20°10'37.65''E, 1289 m, 8.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS.

20. *Phytoecia (Opsilia) coerulescens coerulescens* (Scopoli, 1763)

Opsilia coerulescens, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 301 – Albania; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 231 – “Okol di Boga”, “Pogradec: Dardhas-Gurikamjes, 1200/1400 m”; Siering & Shumka, 2015: 462 – Librazhd, “Dorëz”, “Togëz”, “Zgosht”; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 50 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”, “zwischen Kallamas und Diellas”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 48 – “SE Butrint bei Mursi”, “P.K. Butrinti; N Ksamil; Man. i Shëngjerg”, “Küste; E Orikum; Umgebung Tragjas”, “P.K. Bredhi i Drenovös”, “P.K. Llogara”, “6 km SE Librazhd; Shkumbin-Tal”, “Zentral-Albanien; zwischen Pärrenjas und Qukös; vermülltes Ödland mit vielen Blütenpflanzen; zwischen L. i Shkumbinit und Straße”, “S Gjirokastër; Pass Q. e Muzines; 536 m ü. NN”.

Phytoecia coerulescens, Heyrovský, 1937: 90 – “Lum i Tiranës”; 1967: 581,618 – Albania, “Uji Ftohte südlich Tepelena, 200 m”, “Poligan westlich Tomor, 500 m”, “Iba unterhalb Krraba, 400 m”, “Mali me Grope, Livadhet e Selites, Wiese in 1000-1100 m”, “Bize bei Shëngjergji, 1400-1500 m”; Csiki, 1940: 268 – “Mitrovica”, “Rudnik”, “Ipek”; Schatzmayr, 1943: 134 – “Karburnara”; Muraj, 1960: 141 – “Shumë i rëndomtë Petrelë (Tiranë)”, “Mullet-Ibë”.

Phytoecia (Opsilia) coerulescens coerulescens, Plewa & al., 2018: 181 – “County Korçë: Pustec at Diellas, 850 m a.s.l.”, “County Korçë: Gozhdarazhde at Gërmenj, 990 m a.s.l.”, “County Vlorë: Akerni at Zvërnec”; Danilevsky, 2020: 439 – Albania; 2023: 557.

Material. 3 males, S Albania, Berat County, Skrapar distr., 1 km E Korite vill. Maja e Kulmakes Mts., 40°33'0.06''N, 20°16'36.27''E, 1206 m 21.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 6 males, NW Albania, Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6 km NW Shëngjin, Buna River, Velipoja Protected Landscape, 41°50'16.05''N, 19°31'52.70''E, 5 m, 22.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; Albania, Lezhë County, 6

km WNW Shëngjin sea coast, 41°50'22''N, 19°31'41''E, 22.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML.

21. *Pilemia (Pseudopilemia) hirsutula hirsutula (Frölich, 1793)*

Pilemia hirsutula, Csiki, 1940: 268 – “Mitrovica: Mons Svecan”; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 230 – Albania.

Phytoecia hirsutula, Heyrovský, 1967: 581 – Albania.

Pilemia (Pseudopilemia) hirsutula hirsutula, Danilevsky, 2020: 446 – Albania; Lazarev, 2023c: 73 – Albania.

Material. 1 male, Albania, Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6 km NW Shëngjin, Buna River-Velipoja Protected Landscape, 41°50'16.05"N, 19°31'52.70"E, 5 m, 22.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG.

22. *Agapanthia (Eoptes) boeberi diversicornis Pic, 1927*

Agapanthia cynarae v. *diversicornis* Pic, 1927a: 1 – “Albanie”.

Agapanthia cynarae, Pic, 1927b: 163 – “Albanie: environ de Koritza”; Heyrovský, 1934: 135 – “Skutari, San G. di Medua”, “Tepelene”, “Ljumi Skumbin”, “Devoll-Tal”, “Tomor”, “Kerpice”, “Bushek”; 1967: 581, 615 – Albania, “Iba unterhalb Krraba, 400 m”; Schatzmayr, 1943: 134 – “Lushnja, Skrofotina, Berat, Fushes Dukati e Skendelliut”; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 50 – “des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien”, “zwischen Goricë e Vogël und Liqenas”.

Agapanthia boeberi, Heyrovský, 1937: 90 – Albania: “Lum i Tiranës, Tirane”; Csiki, 1940: 268 (= *cynarae* Germ.) – “Ipek”.

Agapanthia cunerea, Muraj, 1960: 141 (misspelling) – “Zall-ardhë”, “Qaf-Mollë”, “Pasha Liman”, “Bizë”.

Agapanthia cynarae cynarae, Siering & Shumka, 2015: 462 – Librazhd, “Togëz”, “Dorëz”, “Zgoshit”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 47 – “P. K. Butrinti; Ksamil und Umgebung”, “Küste; Orikum; Rruga Sazani”, “P. K. Bredhi i Drenoves”, “Zentral-Albanien; zwischen Perrenjas und Qukes; vermülltes Ödland mit vielen Blütenpflanzen; zwischen L. i Shkumbinit und Straße”, “Gjirokaster; Ebene südlich der Stadt”, “Gjirokaster; Bergland; Krujë”, “S Gjirokaster; Pass Q. e Muzines; 536 m ü. NN”.

Agapanthia (Eoptes) cynarae, Plewa & al., 2018: 181 – “County Gjirokaster: Lëshicë at Përmet, 450 m a.s.l.”, “County Elbasan: Mirakë at Librazhd, 200 m a.s.l.”, “County Elbasan: Hotolisht at Librazhd, 290 m a.s.l.”, “County Shkodër: Hani i Hotit at Ivanaj”.

Agapanthia (Eoptes) cynarae cynarae, Danilevsky, 2023: 595.

Agapanthia (Eoptes) boeberi diversicornis, Lazarev, 2023a: 749 – “Albania, central part of mainland Greece (Athens env., Mt. Parnassos env., Agia Paraskevi, Arta env., Kalambaka env., Leptokaria env., Grevena env., Ossa Mt., Olympus Mts., Vrontou env., Ypati env., Arachova (38°29'41.76"N, 22°34'55.06"E), Amfissa env.)”.

Material. 3 males, 1 female, Albania, Vlorë county, 3.5 km E Vagalat, 80 m, 39°45'43''N, 20°09'39''E, 6.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML; 1 male, S Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Municipality, 0.7 km NE Lefterhor vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'6.73"N, 20° 5'57.13"E, 696 m, 18.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - ML; 1 male, Albania, Vlorë County, 7.5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45"N, 19°31'10.09"E, 810 m., mountain meadows, 16.05.2021, Gubin A.I. leg. - AG.

23. *Agapanthia (Eoptes) asphodeli asphodeli (Latreille, 1804)*

Agapanthia (Eoptes) asphodeli, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 215 – Albania; Danilevsky, 2023: 592.

Agapanthia (Eoptes) asphodeli asphodeli, Danilevsky, 2020: 301 – Albania.

Material. 2 males, S Albania, Vlorë County, 7.5 km SW Vlorë, 5 km S Kanine vill., Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45''N, 19°31'10.09''E, 810 m, 5.5.2021, Yu. Skryllyk leg. - YuS; 1 male, 1 female, Albania, Vlorë County, 4,5 km S Kaninë, Lungar Mts., 40°23'57.34''N, 19°31'5.06''E, 757 m., mountain meadows, 5.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG.

Remark. The taxon is distributed in Albania, Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia.

24. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) schurmanni* Sama, 1979

Figs. 34-35

Material. 3 males, 1 female, Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Munic., 1,5 km NE Varfaj vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'36.28''N, 20°06'10.24''E, 831 m., on *Asphodelina taurica*, 18.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg. - AG; 3 males, with the same label - ML.

Remark. The taxon is distributed in Albania (first record), Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia.

25. *Agapanthia (s. str.) cardui* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Agapanthia cardui, Heyrovsky, 1934: 135 - "Scutari"; 1967: 581, 616 - Albania, "Lukova nördlich Saranda, 250 m"; Schatzmayr, 1943: 134 - "di Terpan, Fushes Dukati e Skrofotina"; Muraj, 1960: 141 - "Shodër; Fier"; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 221 - "Valona"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 214 - Albania; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 46 - "Küste; Orikum", "P. K. Butrinti", "P. K. Butrinti; Ksamil und Umgebung", "SE Butrint bei Mursi; Staudenfluren eines Flusslaufes", "P. K. Butrinti; N Ksamil; Man. i Shöngjerg", "Küste; Orikum; Rruga Sazani", "Küste; E Orikum; Umgebung Tragjas", "Mursi; Seenähe", "S Gjirokastrë; Bergland; Krongj; ruderales Staudenflur"; Danilevsky, 2020: 300 - Albania; 2023: 608.

Material. 4 males, Albania, Vlorë county, 3.5 km E Vagalat, 39°45'43''N, 20°09'39''E, 80 m, 6.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML.

26. *Agapanthia (Smaragdula) violacea* (Fabricius, 1775)

Agapanthia violacea, Heyrovský, 1934: 135 - "San G. di Medua"; 1937: 90 - "Ura Erzen"; 1967: 580, 615 - Albania; Csiki, 1940: 268 - "Deçani"; Muraj, 1960: 141 - "Sauk-Tiranë"; Siering & Shumka, 2015: 462 - Librazhd, "Zgoshit"; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 49 - "des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien", "Kallamas, Gollomboç"; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 47 - "P. K. Butrinti; Ksamil und Umgebung", "SE Butrint bei Mursi", "P.K. Bredhi i Drenoves; Uferzonen des Flusses E des Ortsteiles Drenove".

Agapanthia (s. str.) violacea, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 214 - Albania.

Agapanthia (Smaragdula) violacea, Danilevsky, 2020: 304 - Albania; 2021: 162 - Albania; 2023: 614; Hodek, 2021 - Albania.

Material. 1 male, 1 female, S Albania, Berat County, Skrapar distr., 1 km E Korite vill. Maja e Kulmaka Mts., 40°33'0.06''N, 20°16'36.27''E, 1206 m 21.5.2021, Yu. Skryllyk leg. - YuS.

27. *Tetrops (s. str.) praeustus skryllyki* ssp. n.

Figs. 36-37

Tetrops praeusta, Heyrovský, 1934: 135 - "Logara"; 1937: 90 - "Lum i Tiranes"; 1967: 582, 619 - "Albania"; Csiki, 1940: 268 - "Rudnik"; Siering, Fremuth & Heinemann, 2015: 51 - "des Prespa-Nationalparks in Albanien", "bei Goricë e Vogël";

Tetropium praeustae, Muraj, 1960: 141 - "Sauk-Tiranë", misspelling.

Tetrops praeustus praeustus, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 333 – Albania; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 233 – “Okol di Boga”, “Pogradec: Dardhas-Gurikamjes, 1200/1400 m”; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 48 – “Küste; SE Orikum; Dukat Fshat und Umland”, “P.K. Llogara”, “P.K. Bredhi i Drenoväs; Uferzonen des Flusses E Drenovä”.

Tetrops (s. str.) *praeustus praeustus*, Danilevsky, 2020: 478 – Albania; 2023: 434.

Type locality. Southeastern Albania, Korçë County, Korçë district, 5 km south of Voskopoje, 4 km east of Gjergjevicë village, 40°35'14.97' N, 20°36'0.69' E, 1414 m.

Description. Body black, elytra yellow with black apices, anterior legs about totally yellow, with black femora bases; other legs in males always totally black; same legs colour is often observed in females or in certain females middle and hind legs partly yellowish; frons pubescence in males rather dense, but not hiding frontal punctation; frontal pubescence in females much sparser; male antennae a little shorter than elytra; female antennae much shorter, but sometimes reaching black elytral area; 3rd antennal joint about as long as 1st; prothorax a little shorter than middle width; pronotum with numerous long erect setae, which are considerably denser in males; elytral pubescence relatively short; short semierect setae are distinct near elytral bases only; last abdominal tergite in males rounded, in females – truncated; body length in males: 3.9-4.5 mm, width: 1.0-1.3 mm; body length in females: 4.4-5.5 mm, width: 1.2-1.6 mm.

Differential diagnoses. We use for comparison a series of *T. p. praeustus* (Linnaeus, 1758) from Moscow Region. It strongly differs from Albanien specimens by very long and dense frontal pubescence completely hiding frontal punctation in males; frontal pubescence in females of *T. p. praeustus* is also denser than in *T. p. skrylnyki* **ssp. n.** Elytra in *T. p. praeustus* densely covered with long erect setae from base to apex, though pubescence getting shorter backwards; middle and hind legs in Moscow series never totally black.

Material. Holotype, male, SE Albania, Korçë County, Korçë distr., 5 km S Voskopoje, 4 km E Gjergjevicë vill., 40°35'14.97' N, 20°36'0.69' E, 1414 m, 10.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - ML; 9 paratypes - ML & YuS; 2 males, 3 females with same label; 3 females, S Albania, Gjirokastër County, 5 km E Labovë e Vogël vill., Llofiz Mts., 40°11'16.67' N, 20°11'48.91' E, 1250 m, 8.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg.; 1 female, S Albania, Korçë County, 1 km E Radanj vill., 40°12'38.79" N, 20°37'44.81" E, 1105 m, 9.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg.

Etymology. The new subspecies is dedicated to Yuriy Skrylnyk (Kharkiv), who collected type specimens.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I am very grateful to M. L. Danilevsky (Severtsov Institute of Ecology and Evolution of the Russian Academy of Sciences), I. G. Plyushch (Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology of National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine), Yu. E. Skrylnyk (Laboratory of Forest Protection, Ukrainian Research Institute of Forestry & Forest Melioration) for supplying me with specimens for study.

Figures 1-6. 1-2. Durrës County in the north environs of Durrës (41°20'47"N, 19°25'36."E, 78 m – 41°20'44"N, 19°25'17"E, 70 m), 4.5.2021; 3. *Morimus asper* (Sulzer, 1776), Albania, Durrës County, 2 km westwards Shetaj village, 41°34'04"N, 19°27'54"E, 37 m, 4.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. – YuS; 4-6. Vlorë County, 5.5 km SW Vlorë, 4 km S Kanine vill., Lungar Mts. 40°23'37.45"N, 19°31'10.09"E, 645 m, 5.5.2021; 6 – *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi cynarae* (Germar, 1817).

Figures 7-14. 7. Vlorë County, 17 km NNW Sarande, S env. of Lukove vill., 39°59'0.38"N, 19°54'47.61"E, 150 m, 6.5.2021; 8. Vlorë County, 3,5 km E Vagalat, 81 m., 39°45'43.02"N, 20°9'39.46"E, 6.5.2021; 9-10. Gjirokaštër County, near Saraqinisht village, Lunxhërisë Mts. 40°7'3"N, 20°13'38"E, 900 m, 7.5.2021; 10 – *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917; 11. Gjirokaštër County, 3 km E Labovë e Vogël vill., Llofiz Mts., 40°11'56.30"N, 20°10'37.65"E, 1289 m, 8.5.2021; 12. Gjirokaštër County, 1,6 km N Saraqinishtë vill., Lunxhërisë Mts., 40°7'8.07"N, 20°13'32.78"E, 916 m, 8.5.2021; 13. Gjirokaštër County, 36 km E Gjirokaštër, 1,5 km N Vllaho-Psillotarë vill., 40°6'6.90"N, 20°33'22.38"E, 341 m, 9.5.2021; 14. Korçë County, 0,5 km NW Radanj vill., 40°12'59.35"N, 20°36'51.73"E, 1086 m, 9.5.2021.

Figures 15-21. 15. Korçë County, Korçë distr., 2 km S Voskopoje, 40°36'59.73"N, 20°35'53.84"E, 1321 m, 10.5.2021; 16-17. Korçë County, Korçë distr., 5 km S Voskopoje, 4 km E Gjergjevicë vill., 40°35'14.97"N, 20°36'0.69"E, 1414 m, 10.5.2021; 18. Korçë County, Korçë Municipality, 3 km W Podgorie vill., near Pretusha Reservoir, 40°49'21.51"N, 20°45'48.37"E, 903 m, 11.5.2021; 19. Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1,2 km E Fushë Studë vill., Kodrules Mts., 41°24'16.01"N, 20°25'09.82"E, 1134 m, 12.5.2021; 20. Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6 km NW Shëngjin, Buna River-Velipoja Protected Landscape, 41°50'16.05"N, 19°31'52.70"E, 5 m, 13.V.2021; 21. Vlorë County, 10 km NNW Vlorë, 2,5 km NW Zvërnec, 40°31'22.04"N, 19°23'18.88"E, 1 m, 15.V.2021.

Figures 22-27. 22-25. Vlorë County, 7.5 km SW Vlorë, 5 km S Kanine vill., Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45"N, 19°31'10.09"E, 810 m, 16.5.2021; 24-25 – *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917; 26. Vlorë County, Llogara National Park, Maja e Thanasit Mts., 40°11'52.72"N, 19°35'32.38"E, 1037 m, 17.5.2021; 27. Vlorë County, Delvinë Municipality, 0.7 km NE Lefterhor vill., Kardhiqit Mts., 39°59'6.73"N, 20° 5'57.13"E, 696 m, 18.5.2021.

Figures 28-33. 28. Gjirokaštër County, 13 km NW Gjirokaštër, Taroninë vill. env., 40°7'31.42"N, 20°0'15.66"E, 528 m, 19.V.2021; 29-31. Berat County, Skrapar distr., 1km E Korite vill., Maja e Kulmakes Mts., 40°33'0.06"N, 20°16'36.27"E, 1206 m, 21.5.2021; 32-33. Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6 km NW Shëngjin, Buna River-Velipoja Protected Landscape, 41°50'16.05"N, 19°31'52.70"E, 5 m, 22.5.2021.

Figures 34-35. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) schurmanni* Sama, 1979: 34 – male, Albania, Vlorë County, Delvinë Munic., 1,5 km NE Varfaj vill., Kardihiq Mts., 39°59'36.28"N, 20°06'10.24"E, 831 m., on *Asphodelina taurica*, 18.5.2021, A.I. Gubin leg.; 35 – female, with the same label.

Figures 36-37. *Tetrops (s. str.) praeustus skrylnyki* ssp. n.: 36 – Holotype, male, SE Albania, Korcë County, Korcë distr., 5 km S Voskopoje, 4 km E Gjergjevicë vill., 40°35'14.97"N, 20°36'0.69"E, 1414 m, 10.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg.; 37 – Paratype, female, S Albania, Gjirokastër County, 5 km E Labovë e Vogël vill., Llofiz Mts., 40°11'16.67"N, 20°11'48.91"E, 1250 m, 8.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg.

Map 1. Localities of collected material in Albania.

1. Durrës County in the north environs of Durrës, 41°20'47"N, 19°25'36"E, 78 m, 4.5.2021; 2. Durrës County, 2 km westwards Shetaj village, 41°34'04"N, 19°27'54"E, 37 m, 4.5.2021; 3. Vlorë County, 5.5 km SW Vlorë, 4 km S Kaninë vill., Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45"N, 19°31'10.09"E, 645 m, 5.5.2021; 4. Vlorë County, 17 km NNW Sarandë, S env. of Lukove vill., 39°59'0.38"N, 19°54'47.61"E, 150 m, 6.5.2021; 5. Vlorë County, 3,5 km E Vagalat, 81 m., 39°45'43.02"N, 20°9'39.46"E, 6.5.2021; 6. Gjirokaštër County, near Saraqinisht village, Lunxhërisë Mts. 40°7'3"N, 20°13'38"E, 900 m, 7.5.2021; 7. Gjirokaštër County, 5 km E Labovë e Vogël vill., Llofiz Mts., 40°11'16.67"N, 20°11'48.91"E, 1250 m, 8.5.2021; 8. Gjirokaštër County, 36 km E Gjirokaštër, 1,5 km N Vllaho-Psilloarë vill., 40°6'6.90"N, 20°33'22.38"E, 341 m, 9.5.2021; 9. Korçë County, near Leskovik vill., 40°9'02.52"N, 20°36'21.99"E, 940 m, 9.5.2021; 10. Korçë County, 1 km E Radanj vill., 1105 m, 40°12'38.79"N, 20°37'44.81"E, 9.5.2021; 11. Korçë County, Korçë distr., 5 km S Voskopoje, 4 km E Gjergjević vill., 40°35'14.97"N, 20°36'0.69"E, 1414 m, 10.5.2021; 12. Korçë County, Korçë distr., 2 km S Voskopoje, 40°36'59.73"N, 20°35'53.84"E, 1321 m, 10.5.2021; 13. Korçë County, Korçë Municipality, 1,5 km NE Bregas, That Mts., 40°47'40.43"N, 20°49'34.63"E, 1148 m, 10.5.2021; 14. Korçë County, Pustec Municipality, 3 km S Leskë, Prespa National Park, Maja Kullës Mt., 40°45'3.38"N, 20°53'7.49"E, 1055 m, 11.5.2021; 15. Korçë County, Korçë Municipality, 3 km W Podgorie vill., near Pretusha Reservoir, 40°49'21.51"N, 20°45'48.37"E, 903 m, 11.5.2021; 16. Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1,2 km E Fushë Studë vill., Kodrules Mts., 1134 m., 41°24'16.01"N, 20°25'09.82"E, 12.5.2021; 17. Dibër County, Bulqizë Municipality, 1,5 km W Ostren I Madh vill., 41°25'34.01"N, 20°26'15.42"E, Kodrules Mts., 1148 m., 12.5.2021; 18. Lezhë County, Lezhë distr., 6km NW Shëngjin, Buna River-Velipoja Protected Landscape, 41°50'16.05"N, 19°31'52.70"E, 5 m, 13.5.2021; 19. Vlorë County, 10 km NNW Vlorë, 2,5 km NW Zvërnec, 40°31'22.04"N, 19°23'18.88"E, 1 m., 15.5.2021; 20. Vlorë County, Llogara National Park, Maja e Thanasit Mts., 40°11'52.72"N, 19°35'32.38"E, 1037 m, 17.5.2021; 21. Vlorë County, Delvinë Municipality, 0,7km NE Lefterhor vill., Kardhiq Mts., 39°59'6.73"N, 20°5'57.13"E, 696 m, 18.5.2021; 22. Gjirokaštër County, 13 km NW Gjirokaštër, Taroninë vill. env., 40°7'31.42"N, 20°0'15.66"E, 528 m., 19.5.2021; 23. Berat County, Skrapar distr., 1 km E Koritë vill., Maja e Kulmës Mts., 40°33'0.06"N, 20°16'36.27"E, 1206 m, 21.5.2021.

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